

Research Article

Adsorption of Methylene Blue Dye from Aqueous Solution by using Activated Carbon Orange Peels

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Abstract: Methylene blue (MB) dye present in industrial wastewater is hazardous to the environment and health due to its toxicity and does not degrade easily. Available treatments are expensive and not environmentally friendly, while activated carbon (AC) depends heavily on non-renewable resources. In this study, the adsorption of MB dyes from aqueous solution was performed by using orange peels waste activated carbon (OPWAC) produced through a carbonization and chemical activation using sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄). This study aims to reveal how AC derived from orange peels waste is capable of removing MB dyes effectively. To comprehend the adsorption studies, the effect of concentration varied from 100-500 mg/L were investigated and UV-Vis spectroscopy was employed to quantify the adsorption efficiency by evaluating the decrease in MB's characteristic absorbance near 664 nm. It was found that OPWAC absorbs significant amounts of dye, reaching a maximum capacity of 176.908 mg/g and removing 89.07% of the dye at 500 mg/L and the efficiency rises as the initial dye level in the solution increases, in accordance with adsorption isotherm models. The FTIR analysis confirmed that OPWAC interacted with MB dye and showed various changes in its functional groups during the adsorption process. OPWAC is found as suitable adsorbent that can be used for treating wastewater and recycling agricultural waste, while also supporting circular economy practices.

Keywords: methylene blue dye; adsorption; orange peel waste; activated carbon.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Methylene blue (MB) or methylthioninium chloride is a cationic dye that is commonly used in the textile, paper and staining of biological materials (Yousefi-Limaee et al., 2023). When MB enters waterways, it becomes harmful to people, triggering cyanosis, methemoglobinemia, breathing difficulties and a rapid heartbeat (Zainol et al., 2022). It decreases oxygen widely dissolved in the water and blocks sunlight which negatively affects aquatic plants (Zainol et al., 2022). Due to MB characteristic is chemically stable, it is hard to remove from wastewater and demands proper treatment solutions.

As a result of the growth in Malaysia's textile and manufacturing areas, dye pollution is rising in its water bodies. Conventional methods are expensive and create more waste, requires the need to find sustainable alternatives.

The focus of this research was to explore orange peel as a cost-effective and environmentally friendly way to convert it into activated carbon for removing MB dye. Due to the presence of juice and food industries in Malaysia, orange peels waste is in great supply, making it an eco-friendly way to manage crop waste and wastewater (Zainol et al., 2022). Treating OPW with sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) removes amino groups from its structure, leaving surface groups like hydroxyl and carboxyl that help improve its ability to adsorb (Hameed et al., 2007; Foo & Hameed, 2012). The main objectives of this study was to prepare and analyze how the activation process affects the functional group of untreated and treated OPWAC as well to study and determine the effect of concentrations on the percent removal (%) of MB dye from aqueous solution.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Sample Preparation

The orange peels waste was collected from a local fruit juice shop in Kuching, Sarawak. The orange peels was washed several times with tap and distilled water to remove impurities followed by cutting it into small size and dried in an oven at $105^\circ C$ for 24 h.

2.2 Preparation of adsorbent

The OP waste was separated into two parts for treated and untreated. The dried OP was carbonized in the furnace at a temperature of $400^\circ C$ for 1.5 hours. The produced carbon and untreated were milled into powder and sieved using a $250\mu m$ mesh screen. Next, 20 g of OP carbon was chemically treated in 100mL of 1N H_2SO_4 solution for 1 h. The treated OPWAC were filtered and washed with distilled water until the filtrate reaches pH 7 then left to heat in the oven at temperature of $100^\circ C$ for 2 h.

2.3 Methylene blue dye stock solution

The MB stock solution was prepared by dissolving 1.0 g MB dye powder with purity 82% in 1000 mL distilled water. Specifically, the stock solution was further diluted with distilled water. MB concentrations of 10 to 50 mg/L were prepared from the prepared stock solution by dilution with distilled water. Prior to the adsorption process, UV-Visible spectrophotometric analysis at λ_{max} of 664nm was done on the standard solution to obtain the calibration curve plot. The calibration curve was generated by plotting the observation data recorded against concentration.

2.4 Batch equilibrium study

In this batch adsorption studies, the initial dye concentration was studied was to find out the effectiveness of OPWAC for the MB dye removal from aqueous solutions. The initial dye concentration varied range from 100, 200,300,400 and 500 mg/L were prepared and the pH of MB solution was adjusted to an optimal value of pH 6 by adding 1.0 M HCl and NaOH. A constant amount of 0.25g OPWAC was added in each of dye concentration range with 100 mL volume of MB solution. It was stirred at 200 rpm at room temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ C$) for 120 mins using an incubator orbital shaker. Then, the samples were filtered and residual dye solution were analysed and measured using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

3. FINDINGS

The ability of MB dye to be adsorbed by OPWAC from untreated and treated orange peels was studied at initial concentrations ranging from 100 to 500 mg/L. Removal of dyes by both adsorbents was very effective, reaching 83% or more for different concentrations. The adsorption capacity was highest at 500 ppm OPWAC, with 176.91 mg/g for untreated and 173.70 mg/g for treated OPWAC.

Both materials performed equally well at low concentrations (100 mg/L), while untreated OPWAC displayed a small improvement at mid concentrations. C_e and log-log plots ($\log q_e$ vs. $\log C_e$) consistently showed a similar pattern which indicates that the adsorption process suggesting favourable multilayer adsorption behaviour likely fitting the Freundlich isotherm. Based on the data, both untreated and treated OPWAC work well as inexpensive materials for dye adsorption.

3.1 Characterization of OPWAC using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

FTIR was performed to identify the kinds of functional groups found on the surface of both untreated and treated OPWAC. After being carbonized at 400 °C for 1.5 hours, the treated sample was chemically activated with H_2SO_4 , resulting in significant changes in its surface functional groups. Table 1 below shows the different functional groups that were obtained from the spectra whereas Figure 1 and Figure 2 shows the spectra of untreated and treated orange peels waste activated carbon.

Table 1. Functional group identified from spectra of untreated and treated OPWAC

Sample	Peak Wavelength (cm ⁻¹)	Functional group
Untreated OPWAC	~3300 (broad band)	O-H stretching
	2921.82	C-H stretching (alkyl)
	1575.09	C=C stretching (aromatic ring)
	1380.20	-CH ₃ bending/ COO ⁻ symmetric
Treated OPWAC	~3300 (broad band)	O-H stretching
	2921.53	C-H stretching (alkyl)
	1591.10	C=C stretching (aromatic ring)
	1247.59	C-O stretching (acid, ester, phenol)

Figure 1. FT-IR spectra of untreated orange peels waste activated carbon (OPWAC).

Figure 2. FT-IR spectra of treated orange peels waste activated carbon (OPWAC).

3.2 Effect of initial dye concentration

The effect of initial dye concentration is presented in Figure 3 which shows the removal efficiency (%) and Figure 4 which shows the adsorption capacity (q_e) respectively. With a higher initial concentration of MB dye at 500 mg/L, the adsorption capacity (q_e) of MB on both untreated and treated OPWAC significantly increased compared to 100 mg/L. The percentage of removal did not change much at any concentration, yet in mid-range concentrations of treated OPWAC showed a slight decline since some active sites were filled. This shows that with higher initial dye concentration, there is a greater tendency for dye molecules to be transferred to the adsorbent.

Figure 3. Percent removal of MB dye at the concentration range of 100 to 500 mg/L.

Figure 4. Adsorption capacity, q_e of MB dye at the concentration range of 100 to 500 mg/L

3.3 Adsorption Isotherm

Adsorption isotherm represent the equilibrium behaviour of dye molecules adhering to the surface of an adsorbent. According to the Langmuir isotherm, maximum adsorption capacity can be calculated since it assumes a consistent number of adsorption locations and monolayer coverage. In contrast, Freundlich isotherm deals with heterogeneous surfaces and determined how strongly adsorption occurs and how much material can be adsorbed. Results should highlight the changes in both percentage removal (%) and adsorption capacity (q_e) when the MB concentration is changed, revealing that greater concentration leads to higher adsorption. For isotherm analysis, the linear form of both models was plotted and the constants q_{max} , K_L , K_f and n were calculated. The isotherm model with the highest R^2 value provides the best description of how OPWAC is adsorbed. Adsorption isotherm data of Langmuir and Freundlich for was shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Parameter of adsorption isotherms, Langmuir isotherm and Freundlich isotherm.

Isotherm Model	Parameter	Untreated OPWAC	Treated OPWAC
Langmuir	q_{max} (mg/g)	2.5860	2.6350
	K_L (L/mg)	1E+04	909.0909
	R^2	0.9909	0.9584
Freundlich	K_f (mg/g)(L/mg) ^{1/n}	2.0989	2.2223
	n	0.9379	0.9756
	R^2	0.9702	0.9111

4. DISCUSSION

Table 3 below reveals that, in all concentrations (100–500 mg/L), both the untreated and treated OPWAC removed at least 83% of the methylene blue. Although untreated OPWAC absorption and removal were better (up to 176.91 mg/g and 89.07%, respectively), performance of both materials turned out to be quite comparable. Both adsorbents had almost equal removal rates (nearly 86%) at 100 mg/L, indicating that both had sufficient active sites. Although some decrease in efficiency was found in the range from 200 to 300 mg/L, it was not very different possibly due to altered surface characteristics

post-treatment in the treated surface (Zhao et al., 2017). As a result, treatment did not significantly affect how the material adsorbed dyes, so both types perform well in dye removal.

Table 3. Equilibrium adsorption parameters of MB dye onto untreated and treated OPWAC.

Sample	Co (mg/L)	Ce (mg/L)	qe (mg/g)	% Removal
Untreated	100	13.093	34.360	86.91
	200	28.058	68.448	85.97
	300	42.048	101.769	85.98
	400	52.682	137.262	86.83
	500	54.664	176.908	89.07
Treated	100	13.349	34.531	86.65
	200	33.536	66.040	83.23
	300	48.160	99.897	83.95
	400	53.699	136.089	86.58
	500	54.813	173.698	89.04

4.1 Characterization of OPWAC using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

After treating OPWAC with sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), the FTIR analysis indicates some changes in its chemical composition have occurred. The presence of aliphatic and aromatic functional groups is shown in the untreated sample by C–H and aromatic C=C peaks at 2921.82 and 1575.09 cm^{-1} , respectively. H_2SO_4 treatment leads to the aromatic C=C peak shifting to 1591.10 cm^{-1} which reflects more aromatic condensation caused by acid-induced dehydration and carbonization, supporting the conclusions from similar work by Foo & Hameed (2012). The peak around $\sim 3300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to the stretching of O–H bonds, showed that the functional groups in the sample are hydroxyl groups. The H_2SO_4 treatment makes the band appear broader which is likely due to an increase in polarity and functionalization. A new peak found at 1247.59 cm^{-1} in the treated sample is linked to C–O stretching vibrations, suggesting the presence of oxygen-containing functional groups like carboxylic acids, esters and phenols. These are known to help improve the adsorption efficiency for methylene blue (Zainol et al., 2022). Also, the absence of the 1380.20 cm^{-1} peak implies that methyl or carboxylate groups in the compound may have gone through chemical change or oxidation. Because of these adjustments, the treated material can adsorb more dye since the number of active sites has increased. Thus, using H_2SO_4 on OPWAC not only changes its chemical composition but also boosts its ability to adsorb while remaining inexpensive.

4.2 Effect of initial dye concentration

Methylene blue (MB) adsorption experiments were conducted with concentrations ranging from 100 to 500 mg/L for both treated and untreated adsorbents. Removal rates were nearly the same for both adsorbents (~ 83 – 89%), however at higher concentrations, the treated adsorbent achieved slightly higher results. In contrast, Mousavi et al. (2022) found that the efficiency declined substantially with larger dye amounts because the sites became fully occupied.

As the concentration was increased to 500 mg/L, the adsorption capacity increased to 173.7 mg/g for the treated samples and 176.9 mg/g for the untreated samples. According to Sarkar (2021), the increase in dye uptake at higher concentrations is because the mass transfer force is stronger due to longer contact between the dye solution and the adsorbents.

The slight decrease in efficiency shows that site saturation did not play a major role, particularly for the treated adsorbent. According to Fito et al. (2023), understanding this behaviour is crucial for making effective and scalable adsorption systems. These findings suggest that these adsorbents, especially after treatment with sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), are efficient at removing MB even when the concentration is high, making them suitable for use in treating wastewater.

4.3 Adsorption Isotherm

The Langmuir and Freundlich models were commonly used to study the equilibrium data of MB adsorption onto untreated and treated OPWAC. In the Langmuir isotherm, the adsorption is believed to happen as a single layer on an equal and limited number of identical sites. The linear form is given by the equation below:

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{Q_m K_L} + \frac{C_e}{Q_m}$$

where C_e is the equilibrium concentration (mg/L), q_e is the amount of dye absorbed at equilibrium (mg/g), Q_m is the maximum adsorption capacity (mg/g) and K_L is the Langmuir constant (L/mg). The separation factor $R_L = \frac{1}{1+K_L C_0}$ which is a crucial parameter obtained from this model which denotes the adsorption is considered favourable if values of $0 < R_L < 1$ are obtained. In contrast, the linear form of the Freundlich isotherm, which describes adsorption on heterogeneous surfaces, is as follows:

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e$$

where K_f is the Freundlich constant indicated adsorption capacity, $1/n$ represents the adsorption intensity. When value of $1/n$ is between 0 and 1, it means a favourable, nonlinear adsorption. Among these two isotherm models, the Freundlich model is likely to fit both adsorption material although Langmuir shown a higher correlation coefficients, R^2 values which were 0.9909 and 0.9584 for untreated and treated OPWAC compared to the Freundlich model which the R^2 values were 0.9702 and 0.9111 respectively. This implies that the MB is absorbed onto OPWAC surface by a process involving layers of molecules attached to various areas of the surface.

According to these results, the q_{exp} for treated OPWAC (173.70 mg/g) was much larger than the calculation q_{max} based on Langmuir (2.635 mg/g). The gap happens because the linearized Langmuir model can underestimate q_{max} , mainly when dealing with heterogeneous or porous materials. Hence, such distinction confirms the effectiveness of the Freundlich isotherm for explaining OPWAC adsorption. Also, the high values of K_f for both untreated 2.0989 (mg/g)(L/mg) $^{1/n}$ and treated OPWAC 2.2223 (mg/g)(L/mg) $^{1/n}$ show that MB molecules are strongly attracted to the surfaces of the adsorbents. Previously, research has shown that adsorption on biomass-derived activated carbons for dye removal can be described by Freundlich isotherms, especially after surface treatment that provides more active sites for adsorption (Foo & Hameed, 2010).

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study has successfully achieved its objectives in which the untreated and treated orange peels waste activated carbon (OPWAC) were prepared and the activation process that affects its functional group was analyzed as well as the effect of concentration on the percentage removal (%) and adsorption capacity, q_e (mg/g) of MB dye from aqueous solution were studied and determined. It was shown that OPWAC, both treated and untreated, is effective at removing methylene blue (MB) dye from aqueous solution. The higher the dye concentration, the more sorbent able to

adsorb. According to the FTIR data, after treating with sulfuric acid, OPWAC now contains more oxygen containing surface functional groups which improves its ability to adsorb.

Based on the adsorption isotherm, it was determined that the Freundlich model fits best for both untreated OPWAC and treated OPWAC, revealing that the surfaces are heterogeneous and allow MB dye to be adsorbed into multiple layers. Remarkably, the untreated OPWAC performed slightly better in adsorption than the treated one, implying that surface treatment here did not improve the capacity for adsorbing impurities. The study has shown that converted orange peel waste activated carbon even with no chemical treatment can serve as a useful, affordable and eco-friendly adsorbent to remove dyes from wastewater and help combat environmental issues in Malaysia.

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